

THE MOST COMMON GYNECOLOGICAL DISEASES, EROSIONS IN WOMEN.

Iskanderova Guzal Kamilovna

The leading teacher of the Tashkent Vocational and Medical Technical College

Annotation: This article is about gynecological diseases. Because all organs and systems are interconnected, women's diseases should be considered as a disease of the whole body. Gynecological diseases, in turn, can occur as a result of diseases of other organs and systems. Various specific and non-specific infections, childhood diseases, endocrine diseases, metabolic disorders, pathology of vital organs are of primary importance.

Key words: erosion, gynecological, diseases, organ, woman, infection, chronic, cause, vaginal, hormonal disorders, decreased immunity, menstrual cycle disorders.

Cervical erosion (endocervicosis, cervical ectopy) is a violation of the integrity of the mucous membrane in the vaginal part of the organ, defect or covering with wounds. Erosion opens the way for infection to enter the uterus and its appendages and causes the development of chronic inflammatory diseases of the small pelvis, and can even lead to infertility.

At the gynecologist's appointment, almost every second patient is diagnosed with cervical erosion. In general, this disease is one of the most common pathologies in women of childbearing age. The most dangerous complication of uterine erosion is the possibility that it will turn into a tumor of poor quality. Therefore, it is very important to detect this disease as soon as possible.

There are many causes of pathology and factors that stimulate its development, the main ones are:

- Hormonal disorders and decreased immunity;

- Menstrual cycle disorders;
- Very early onset of sexual life, as well as early pregnancy and childbirth;
- Frequent change of sexual partners;
- Non-observance of personal hygiene;
- Mechanical as a result of difficult childbirth, abortion and other medical manipulations injuries;
- Improper use of vaginal contraceptives or incorrect rinsing, very rough sex;
- Inflammatory and infectious diseases of the genitourinary system, including their late and incorrect treatment;
- Bacterial and viral diseases;
- Heredity.

The situation with erosion of the cervix is complicated by the fact that this disease does not have clear symptoms and in most cases it does not show itself at all. But with the development of erosion, patients can identify the following symptoms:

- Discharge of bloody and sometimes purulent discharge between menstruations, for example, after sexual intercourse;
- Unpleasant-smelling vaginal discharge;
- Menstruation lasts longer than usual, more bleeding;
- Pain in the lower abdomen during urination or sexual intercourse.

In any case, a colposcopy is also performed (examination of the cervix and vagina under magnification) and a smear is taken and analyzed from the surface of the erosion to rule out oncological diseases. Examination of the cervix with an optical device that increases the image by 25-32 times is absolutely painless.

Diagnosis of the pathology is somewhat complicated due to the fact that there is no specific symptom of the disease, and the conditions that cause the patient to complain are not observed.

During the examination of the patient, the gynecologist first examines the cervix using mirrors. As a result, epithelial defects in the form of a bright red spot on the background of healthy tissue, which bleed when in contact with a gynecological instrument, can be identified on its mucous membrane. Depending on the type of erosion, there are other external signs of the disease. True erosions appear bright pink, areas of dysplasia appear yellow, and atypical foci appear fluid. If mucosal dysplasia is suspected, a biopsy sample is taken from the area and a histological examination is performed.

When the disease is detected, it is necessary not to be afraid of it, especially considering that there are many treatment methods available today. Instead, you should be careful about the consequences of not getting treatment on time, because it can lead to various complications before the onset of cancer.

Today, erosion is effectively treated, so there is no need to treat it independently at home, to use folk remedies, which, even if they give the impression of being effective, can aggravate the existing situation.

References:

1. Abdullayevich, B. E., & Uchqun o'g'li, B. S. (2021). TRANSITIONAL FEATURES OF ACUTE HERPETIC STOMATITIS IN CHILDREN AND MODERN APPROACHES TO TREATMENT. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 1(1), 1-3.
2. Uchqun o'g'li, B. S. Bulvar And Pseudobulbar Syndrome. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(11), 19-22
3. Madiyev Rustam Zoirovich, Boboyorov Sardor Uchqun o'g'li, & Abdullaeva Dilnoza Ergashevna. (2021). EFFECTIVENESS OF ENDOVIDEOLAPAROSCOPIC TECHNOLOGY IN THE TREATMENT AND EARLY PREVENTION OF INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION IN CHILDREN. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(7), 68-73.

INNOVATIVE OFFERS IN EDUCATION AND SOCIETY

American International Open Conference 2024

<http://innconferences.iblogger.org/>

